

FILLER RESCUE APP: ALGORITHM-DRIVEN CLINICAL DECISION SUPPORT FOR VASCULAR AND NEURO-OPHTHALMIC FILLER EVENTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The expanding use of hyaluronic acid dermal fillers has been accompanied by persistent risks of vascular occlusion, neuro-ophthalmic ischemia, anaphylaxis, and late inflammatory reactions. Although expert guidelines provide comprehensive diagnostic and therapeutic frameworks, real-time implementation during acute events remains challenging. This study describes the conceptualization and development of the Filler Rescue (FR) App, a medical-grade digital decision-support system designed to translate evidence-based consensus recommendations into structured, real-time clinical workflows.

Materials and Methods: A structured qualitative synthesis was conducted using the three most recently published peer-reviewed guidelines addressing cutaneous vascular occlusion, neuro-ophthalmic ischemia, and emergency pharmacologic preparedness. Key diagnostic criteria, ischemic staging models, angiosome classifications, pharmacologic algorithms, and escalation pathways were extracted and translated into event-driven digital decision trees. Algorithms were reconstructed to preserve temporal ischemic logic and therapeutic sequencing. Development was performed collaboratively by **three team ?** expert physicians and an information technology team. The platform incorporates time tracking, automated dosage prompts, escalation alerts, version-controlled guideline governance, audit logging, and GDPR-compliant data security architecture. Internal simulation testing using standardized complication scenarios was conducted to evaluate navigation clarity and decision latency.

Results: The FR App operationalizes guideline-derived frameworks into interactive, stage-adapted workflows for vascular, neuro-ophthalmic, anaphylactic, and inflammatory complications. Integrated specialist consultation pathways and pharmacologic inventory monitoring enhance escalation readiness and emergency preparedness. Usability simulations demonstrated coherent algorithm activation and reduced navigation complexity under stress conditions.

Conclusion: The FR App represents a structured digital translation of expert consensus guidelines into a real-time clinical decision-support environment.

Keywords: dermal fillers; hyaluronic acid; vascular occlusion; neuro-ophthalmic ischemia; anaphylaxis; digital health; clinical decision support systems; emergency preparedness; patient safety.

Level of Evidence: Level V

INTRODUCTION

The use of dermal fillers, particularly hyaluronic acid–based products, has increased substantially in aesthetic medicine due to their effectiveness and favorable safety profile. Nevertheless, complications such as cutaneous vascular occlusion, neuro-ophthalmic ischemia, anaphylaxis, and late-onset inflammatory reactions continue to occur and require immediate, structured, and evidence-based management to prevent morbidity [1–3].

Although comprehensive expert guidelines provide detailed diagnostic and therapeutic frameworks, including ischemia staging, angiosome-based assessment, time-dependent intervention strategies, and protocolized pharmacologic treatment [1–3], their real-time implementation in outpatient practice remains challenging. Acute complications are often characterized by time pressure and heightened cognitive demand, which may impair the stepwise application of complex algorithms and adherence to best practice recommendations.

Digital medical applications have emerged as potential tools to support point-of-care decision-making; however, evidence indicates that only applications grounded in validated scientific frameworks, standardized quality criteria, and robust usability standards demonstrate meaningful clinical utility and safety [4–10]. In particular, the need for transparent evaluation models and regulatory-aligned development processes has been emphasized in recent analyses of medical health applications [4–6]. In this context, there is a clear need for medical-grade decision-support systems capable of translating consensus recommendations into actionable clinical pathways.

Filler Rescue (FR) Application (App) was developed to address this gap by transforming evidence-based clinical guidelines [1–3] into structured, real-time

digital algorithms designed specifically for the management of filler-related complications. The platform functions as a clinical decision-support companion during acute events, providing guided diagnostic pathways, protocol-driven emergency pharmacologic management, integrated pharmacy checklists, continuously updated evidence-based recommendations, and access to online medical advisory support. By converting static consensus documents into interactive, stepwise digital workflows, FR App seeks to standardize emergency responses, reduce cognitive burden under stress, and enhance patient safety in aesthetic practice. This article presents the conceptual framework, development methodology, and clinical implementation model of the FR App, evaluating its role as a structured digital decision-support tool for the management of dermal filler-related complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of FR App (Fillerrescue Llc, Delaware, USA) was based on a structured qualitative synthesis of three contemporary articles and expert guidelines addressing vascular and pharmacologic complications associated with hyaluronic acid (HA) dermal fillers: Guide for Managing Vascular Occlusion Caused by Fillers with Exclusive Cutaneous Involvement: A Review of Diagnosis, Classification, and Treatment [1]; Guide for Managing Vascular Occlusion Due to Fillers with Extended Neuro-Ophthalmic Involvement: A Review of Diagnosis, Classification and Treatment [2]; and Essential Pharmaceutical Drugs in the Filler Emergency Kit [3]. These documents were selected for their methodological rigor, recency, and direct clinical applicability.

From the cutaneous vascular occlusion guideline [1], key diagnostic and therapeutic frameworks were extracted, including clinical and ultrasound-based diagnosis, time-dependent ischemic staging, angiosome-based classification, and structured treatment algorithms incorporating high-dose hyaluronidase (HYAL), antiplatelet therapy (APT), vasodilators, anti-inflammatory measures, debridement strategies, and escalation criteria aligned with ischemic progression.

The neuro-ophthalmic guideline [2] contributed analysis of embolic etiology, temporal neuro-ophthalmic classification, structured ophthalmic and neurological

diagnostic approaches, stroke classification systems, multimodal imaging strategies, and integrated evaluation models. Therapeutic recommendations included intraocular pressure reduction, multiple HYAL administration routes, APT, selective intra-arterial interventions, hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) considerations, and stroke management pathways consistent with established cerebrovascular guidelines.

The pharmacologic guideline [3] provided an evidence-based framework for emergency medication protocols covering vascular occlusion with and without ocular involvement, late inflammatory reactions, anaphylaxis, cardiopulmonary resuscitation, and hemodynamic instability. Drug dosing, contraindications, escalation thresholds, and standardized emergency kit configurations were incorporated to ensure operational readiness.

This study was performed by three expert aesthetic physicians specialized in vascular events with extensive clinical experience in complication management (N.F-G., J.M-P., L.A.) to identify convergent diagnostic criteria, therapeutic sequences, and pharmacologic algorithms. Extracted elements were translated into event-driven digital workflows designed to support physicians managing high-stress clinical scenarios, preserving temporal ischemic logic, differentiation of complication type, and protocol-linked pharmacologic sequencing. The digital platform was developed by an experienced information technology team in close collaboration with these three physicians, ensuring accurate translation of clinical algorithms into a secure, usable, and medically robust software architecture.

Data governance was structured in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Infrastructure is hosted exclusively within the European Economic Area (AWS eu-central-1, Frankfurt), under a GDPR-compliant Data Processing Addendum. Health data are processed based on explicit patient consent (Art. 9(2)(a) GDPR) and protected through AES-256 encryption at rest, TLS 1.2+ encryption in transit, multi-factor authentication, role-based access control, and comprehensive audit logging. The platform is available in twelve languages to support international clinical collaboration without altering the underlying evidence-based clinical logic.

RESULTS

The platform operationalizes guideline derived diagnostic, therapeutic, and pharmacologic frameworks into structured digital workflows designed for real time complication management.

1. Structured clinical case management and algorithm Activation

A dedicated clinical case management module was developed to enable comprehensive documentation and dynamic handling of filler related adverse events. The module allows secure registration of patient identifiers, **registro fotografico** relevant medical history, treatment parameters, and detailed clinical findings.

Upon case activation, the system automatically initiates a real time event timer that records elapsed time from symptom onset. This temporal tracking feature was specifically designed to reinforce the time dependent therapeutic windows defined in the cutaneous and neuro ophthalmic guidelines [1,2]. Continuous visualization of elapsed time enhances physician awareness of ischemic thresholds and supports prioritization of urgent stage specific interventions.

Primero se clasifica temporalmente en Early/late y Delayed . Early se divide en Immediate <4h , penumbra 4-6 hy dereferred > 6h. LA app incorpora un algoritmo de diagnostico validado en el articulo "afectacion cutanea exclusive" [1] y que facilita y guia en el diagnostico de la oclusion vascular. La cegera o el stroke son criterios mayores de oclusion vascular mientras para la afeccion cutanea debe cumplir un minimo de criterios menores. Confirmada la oclusion vascular por criterios o por decision clinica ~~In suspected vascular occlusion~~, clinicians identify the affected angiosome using the FOEM2 classifications as described in the cutaneous guideline [1]. Following angiosome selection and temporal ischemic stratification into immediate, penumbra, or delayed phases, the system activates a stage adapted therapeutic algorithm derived from the integrated cutaneous and neuro ophthalmic frameworks [1,2].

The algorithm generates a dynamic stepwise pathway that guides the clinician through high dose and repeated HYAL administration (reevaluacion continua cada 20 minutos con alarmas) tailored to angiosome involvement, integration of APT, consideration of vasodilatory and adjunctive anti-inflammatory measures, structured reassessment intervals, and clearly defined escalation criteria. In addition, the system provides automated dosage prompts based on guideline parameters, predefined documentation fields to ensure procedural traceability, visual alerts for ischemic time thresholds, and integrated checklists to reduce omission errors during high stress scenarios. In cases of suspected ophthalmic involvement, the system activates a dedicated neuro-ophthalmic management algorithm derived from the extended vascular occlusion guideline [2]. The workflow guides clinicians through temporal classification of visual loss, structured assessment of residual visual function, and ischemic urgency stratification. Sequential prompts reinforce immediate intraocular pressure reduction, initiation of antiplatelet therapy, high-dose HYAL administration at the cutaneous embolic origin, and extraorbital HYAL injections targeting the supratrochlear and supraorbital arteries with predefined reassessment intervals. When appropriate expertise is available, guidance for peribulbar or retrobulbar HYAL administration is included. The algorithm further incorporates prompts for urgent ophthalmologic consultation, neurological evaluation, stroke code activation, and referral to tertiary centers for potential intra-arterial intervention. Integration within the real-time event timer preserves adherence to time-dependent therapeutic windows.

This module converts static consensus recommendations into an interactive, time sensitive clinical decision support environment designed to assist physicians during acute adverse events. The platform functions exclusively as an adjunctive decision support tool; ultimate clinical judgment, therapeutic decisions, and responsibility remain entirely with the treating physician.

2. Specialist consultation and escalation pathway

A second structured domain enables direct consultation with physicians specialized in filler related complications. Through a secure interface, users may

request emergency or non-emergency assistance, activating synchronous videoconferencing or encrypted real time chat within the platform.

This module facilitates rapid multidisciplinary case discussion, structured review of clinical documentation and imaging, and real time therapeutic validation including guidance on escalation thresholds. It also supports early coordination of referral pathways in cases of suspected neuro ophthalmic ischemia or cerebrovascular events.

By embedding specialist access within the same digital clinical environment, the platform operationalizes the escalation principles emphasized in the neuro ophthalmic guideline [2], particularly in time dependent visual or neurologic compromise. This integration reinforces structured evidence-based decision making under acute clinical conditions.

3. Pharmacologic preparedness and filler emergency kit

The pharmacologic framework described in Essential Pharmaceutical Drugs in the Filler Emergency Kit [3] was translated into an integrated digital pharmacy management system. Medications are categorized according to an ORA model, defined as Obligatory, Recommended, and Additional, reflecting hierarchical priority levels in emergency preparedness.

The structured inventory encompasses pharmacologic agents indicated for vascular occlusion with or without ocular involvement, medications required for the management of neuro ophthalmic ischemia, therapies for late onset inflammatory adverse events, agents for anaphylaxis management, and drugs essential for cardiopulmonary resuscitation and hemodynamic stabilization. The inventory is designed to support emergency preparedness; however, medication selection, dosing, and administration remain under the full responsibility of the treating physician. Anticoagulation strategies, sterile preparation materials, and all required procedural supplies, as well as relevant topical therapeutic agents, are incorporated into the digital framework. Users may document available stock and expiration dates for each item. Automated alerts are generated when mandatory medications are absent, insufficient in quantity, or approaching

expiration. This monitoring system ensures continuous alignment between algorithm based therapeutic recommendations and real-world pharmacologic readiness, thereby strengthening emergency preparedness in daily clinical practice.

4. Protocol repository and algorithm library

A centralized protocol repository was implemented to provide structured access to interactive management algorithms derived from the integrated guidelines [1-3]. The repository includes comprehensive pathways for vascular occlusion encompassing both cutaneous and neuro ophthalmic involvement, as well as structured algorithms for anaphylaxis and late onset adverse events.

Each protocol preserves the temporal urgency, ischemic staging logic, pharmacologic sequencing, escalation criteria, and referral pathways defined in the source guidelines. Algorithms may be activated during acute emergencies or accessed for preventive review in non-acute settings.

This unified digital framework promotes clinical standardization, operational preparedness, and continuous professional education while maintaining fidelity to consensus-based recommendations.

5. System architecture and guideline governance

The platform was developed using a modular architecture in which each clinical domain is structured as an independent but interoperable algorithmic component. Decision trees were directly mapped from guideline source documents [1–3] through a structured translation process involving clinical content decomposition, logical branching reconstruction, and validation against original staging and therapeutic sequences to preserve conceptual fidelity.

Each algorithm is version controlled, with documented update logs linked to guideline revisions or emerging evidence. Content updates follow a predefined review pathway that includes expert reassessment and internal validation prior to deployment. This governance structure ensures traceability between digital workflows and their source consensus recommendations.

6. Data security and compliance framework

The platform incorporates a structured data security architecture designed to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and traceability of clinical information. Secure authentication protocols, multi factor authentication, and role-based access control are implemented to restrict system access according to user privileges. All data transmissions are protected using Transport Layer Security encryption, and stored data are secured through Advanced Encryption Standard 256-bit encryption at rest.

Clinical case documentation is maintained within a secure cloud infrastructure hosted exclusively within the European Economic Area (AWS eu central 1, Frankfurt) under a Data Processing Addendum aligned with Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Health data processing is conducted on the basis of explicit patient consent in accordance with Article 9(2)(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation.

Comprehensive audit logging mechanisms record algorithm activation, therapeutic pathway selection, documentation edits, and specialist consultation requests. These logs enable procedural traceability, facilitate quality control, and support medicolegal audit capability.

The system is explicitly designed as a clinical decision support tool and does not operate autonomously. All diagnostic interpretations, therapeutic decisions, and pharmacologic interventions require active physician review and confirmation.

To support international use while preserving clinical integrity, the platform is available in twelve languages. Linguistic adaptation does not modify the underlying evidence based algorithmic structure, thereby ensuring consistency of guideline fidelity across jurisdictions.

7. Usability and stress scenario testing

Pre implementation internal simulation testing was performed using standardized complication scenarios to evaluate algorithm navigation clarity, decision latency,

and pathway coherence. Iterative refinements were introduced to reduce cognitive load, improve interface logic, and optimize emergency usability.

This structured testing phase was conducted to ensure that algorithm activation remained intuitive and operationally efficient under simulated acute care conditions.

DISCUSSION

The increasing global use of HA-based dermal fillers has been accompanied by a proportional rise in procedure-related complications, including vascular occlusion, neuro-ophthalmic ischemia, anaphylaxis, and late-onset inflammatory reactions [1–3]. Although contemporary guidelines provide comprehensive diagnostic and therapeutic frameworks [1–3], their practical application during acute events remains complex.

One of the principal contributions of this platform lies in the structured translation of guideline documents into interactive decision trees while preserving temporal ischemic logic, angiosome classification, pharmacologic sequencing, and escalation criteria [1–3]. Acute filler-related vascular events are characterized by narrow therapeutic windows, particularly in cases of neuro-ophthalmic involvement where irreversible visual loss may occur within minutes [2]. Under such time-critical conditions, cognitive overload and stress may compromise adherence to complex stepwise protocols.

By incorporating automated time tracking, stage-specific alerts, dosage prompts, and predefined reassessment intervals, the system was designed to reduce omission errors and reinforce adherence to evidence-based recommendations [1–3]. Importantly, the platform does not replace clinical judgment but functions as an adjunctive support tool. Final interpretation and therapeutic decisions remain exclusively under physician responsibility, thereby preserving the primacy of individualized medical care.

The integration of a structured specialist consultation pathway addresses a recognized gap in complication management. Vascular events associated with filler procedures require rapid expert support to minimize tissue ischemia and

prevent irreversible sequelae [1–3]. The specialist consultation module operationalizes this need by enabling real-time access to physicians experienced in the management of filler-related complications. This functionality may be particularly valuable in regions where immediate subspecialty expertise is not locally available, thereby potentially reducing delays in escalation and enhancing coordination of care.

This operationalization of escalation logic aligns with broader principles of emergency medicine, where standardized pathways and early specialist involvement are associated with improved process metrics. While outcome data are not yet available, the structural integration of consultation workflows represents a systems-based approach to complication management.

The centralized protocol repository further contributes to standardization and continuous education. By consolidating vascular occlusion, anaphylaxis, and late-onset adverse event (LOAE) algorithms into an interactive digital library, the system promotes consistent application of evidence-based pathways [1–3] while also serving as a preventive training tool in non-emergency settings. This dual function—acute activation and preventive review—may enhance both preparedness and long-term adherence to best-practice standards.

A frequent limitation in outpatient aesthetic practice is inconsistency in emergency kit preparedness. By converting pharmacologic guidelines into an ORA-categorized inventory system with automated alerts for stock deficiencies and expiration monitoring, the platform extends beyond decision support into operational governance [3]. This feature addresses a critical but often underreported determinant of patient safety: the immediate availability of appropriate medications and supplies. The linkage between algorithmic recommendations and pharmacologic readiness may reduce treatment delays [3].

The implementation of version-controlled algorithms, structured update pathways, audit logging, and data protection measures aligned with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 enhances the platform's transparency and traceability. In the context of digital health tools, regulatory compliance and data governance are not

merely technical considerations but determinants of clinical trust and medico-legal robustness [4–10].

The explicit positioning of the system as a clinical decision-support tool rather than an autonomous diagnostic system is consistent with current regulatory distinctions in digital medicine and governance frameworks [4–10]. Ensuring that all therapeutic decisions require active physician confirmation maintains alignment with ethical and legal standards of medical responsibility.

While numerous mobile applications exist within aesthetic medicine, few are grounded in formally published guidelines or incorporate structured governance mechanisms [4–10]. Many commercially available tools emphasize educational content rather than real-time, stage-adapted algorithm activation. The distinguishing characteristic of the present system lies in its direct derivation from peer-reviewed consensus documents [1–3] and its structured mapping of those documents into executable workflows. However, unlike randomized clinical trials evaluating therapeutic interventions, the present study describes a systems development initiative. Therefore, its contribution is primarily methodological and structural rather than outcome-based.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the present study does not provide prospective clinical outcome data demonstrating improved complication resolution rates, reduced ischemic progression, or decreased incidence of visual loss [1–3]. This work describes the methodological translation of expert consensus guidelines into a structured digital architecture but does not evaluate clinical outcomes, rates of guideline adherence, or measurable reductions in physician stress. Accordingly, the platform's potential to enhance patient safety and decision-making under high-stress conditions remains theoretical until validated in prospective real-world studies [4–10]. The evaluation focused primarily on structured guideline translation, usability testing, and governance architecture rather than comparative effectiveness.

Second, usability assessment was conducted through internal simulation scenarios rather than large-scale multicenter validation. Although iterative refinements were implemented to optimize navigation clarity and reduce cognitive

burden, formal human factors engineering analysis and external validation studies are warranted to establish reproducibility and generalizability [4–10].

Third, reliance on guideline-based algorithms inherently reflects the quality, strength, and limitations of the underlying source literature [1–3]. As new evidence emerges, ongoing algorithm revision and structured content updates will be required to preserve clinical relevance and alignment with evolving standards of care.

Finally, although the platform supports international collaboration through multilingual deployment, variations in regional regulatory frameworks, medication availability, and healthcare infrastructure may influence practical implementation. Adaptation to local clinical contexts and continuous content governance will be essential to ensure safe and effective global use [4–10].

Future research should prospectively evaluate clinically meaningful endpoints, including time to intervention, adherence to recommended dosing protocols, timing of referral to specialized care, complication resolution rates, and user-reported stress metrics during acute management. Such outcome-based evaluation will be essential to determine whether digital decision support translates into measurable improvements in patient safety and process efficiency [4–10].

Despite these limitations, the structured operationalization of evidence-based guidelines into a digital decision-support environment represents a step toward standardization of filler complication management [1–3]. By combining algorithmic guidance, pharmacologic readiness monitoring, specialist escalation pathways, and regulatory-aligned governance, the platform addresses multiple determinants of patient safety within aesthetic practice.

In a field where severe complications such as blindness and stroke carry profound consequences [2], systems designed to reduce variability and reinforce evidence-based action may contribute to improved procedural safety culture. Continued validation and real-world evaluation will determine the measurable clinical impact of such digital tools [4–10].

CONCLUSION

FR App represents a structured digital translation of evidence-based guidelines into a real time clinical decision support system for dermal filler related complications. By integrating ischemic staging, angiosome classification, pharmacologic algorithms, specialist escalation pathways, and emergency kit governance, the platform aims to reduce practice variability and support time sensitive decision making in acute scenarios.

Designed as an adjunctive tool under full physician oversight, it prioritizes guideline fidelity, procedural traceability, and regulatory alignment. FR App offers an innovative framework to bridge the gap between expert consensus and real-world clinical implementation, with the potential to enhance standardization, preparedness, and physician support in the management of high risk filler related adverse events.

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Ethics statement. This article does not contain any studies with humans or animals performed by any of the authors.

Consent to publish. All photographs do not require any consent for the publication.

Data policy. For this type of study, we don't have data to deposit in a public repository.

REFERENCES

1. Madero-Pérez J, Gil-Martinez M, Muñoz-Gonzalez C, Fakh D, Martin-Marfil P, Fakh-Gomez N. Guide for Managing Vascular Occlusion Caused by Fillers with Exclusive Cutaneous Involvement: A Review of Diagnosis, Classification, and Treatment. *Aesthetic Plast Surg.* 2025 Aug 6. doi: 10.1007/s00266-025-05104-3. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 40770496.

2. Madero-Pérez J, et al. Guide for managing vascular occlusion due to fillers with extended neuro-ophthalmic involvement: a review of diagnosis, classification, and treatment. *Aesthetic Plast Surg* 2025. In press.
3. Madero-Pérez J, Gil-Martinez M, Muñoz-Gonzalez C, Martin-Marfil P, Fakh-Gomez N. Essential Pharmaceutical Drugs in the Filler Emergency Kit. *Aesthetic Plast Surg*. 2025 Jul;49(14):4043-4056. doi: 10.1007/s00266-025-04808-w. Epub 2025 Mar 31. PMID: 40164895.
4. Deniz-Garcia A, Fabelo H, Rodriguez-Almeida AJ, Zamora-Zamorano G, Castro-Fernandez M, Alberiche Ruano MDP, Solvoll T, Granja C, Schopf TR, Callico GM, Soguero-Ruiz C, Wägner AM; WARIFA Consortium. Quality, Usability, and Effectiveness of mHealth Apps and the Role of Artificial Intelligence: Current Scenario and Challenges. *J Med Internet Res*. 2023 May 4;25:e44030. doi: 10.2196/44030. PMID: 37140973; PMCID: PMC10196903.
5. Chong SOK, Pedron S, Abdelmalak N, Laxy M, Stephan AJ. An umbrella review of effectiveness and efficacy trials for app-based health interventions. *NPJ Digit Med*. 2023 Dec 16;6(1):233. doi: 10.1038/s41746-023-00981-x. PMID: 38104213; PMCID: PMC10725431.
6. Maass L, Freye M, Pan CC, Dassow HH, Niess J, Jahnel T. Health and medical apps - Same same but different? A review of definitions in public health and law. *Eur J Public Health*. 2022 Oct 25;32(Suppl 3):ckac131.165. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckac131.165. PMCID: PMC9834990.
7. Giebel GD, Speckemeier C, Schrader NF, Abels C, Plescher F, Hillerich V, Wiedemann D, Borchers K, Wasem J, Blase N, Neusser S. Quality assessment of mHealth apps: a scoping review. *Front Health Serv*. 2024 May 1;4:1372871. doi: 10.3389/frhs.2024.1372871. PMID: 38751854; PMCID: PMC11094264.
8. Henson P, David G, Albright K, Torous J. Deriving a practical framework for the evaluation of health apps. *Lancet Digit Health*. 2019 Jun;1(2):e52-e54. doi: 10.1016/S2589-7500(19)30013-5. Epub 2019 May 23. PMID: 33323229.

9. Grundy Q. A Review of the Quality and Impact of Mobile Health Apps. *Annu Rev Public Health*. 2022 Apr 5;43:117-134. doi: 10.1146/annurev-publhealth-052020-103738. Epub 2021 Dec 15. PMID: 34910582.
10. Mescher, T., Hacker, R.L., Martinez, L.A. *et al*. Mobile Health Apps: Guidance for Evaluation and Implementation by Healthcare Workers. *J. technol. behav. sci.* 10, 224–235 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41347-024-00441-7>.

LEGENDS

Figure 1. Application navigation menu displaying user profile information and access to core modules, including appointments, cases, protocols, pharmacy, language settings, FAQs, and logout functionality.

Figure 2. Main Dashboard and Case Management Interface. A. Home screen of the medical application displaying the user dashboard with registered patient cases and upcoming appointments. The interface provides direct access to core modules, including cases, specialists, pharmacy, and clinical protocols. B. Case management interface of the medical application showing the searchable and filterable patient list. The screen includes sorting functions, case dates, and the option to create a new case entry, facilitating structured clinical documentation and follow-up.

Figure 3. Individual patient profile within the medical application displaying standardized clinical photographs (frontal and lateral views), demographic information, and structured medical history. The interface includes documented comorbidities, previous filler history, allergy status, and access to current treatment records, supporting comprehensive clinical assessment and longitudinal follow-up.

Figure 4. Clinical decision-support workflow for suspected vascular occlusion. A. Vascular occlusion assessment interface within the medical application. The screen displays temporal classification (early/immediate presentation) and structured documentation of major and minor clinical signs, including pain intensity, skin color changes, capillary refill time, edema/turgor, and ischemic response to puncture testing. B. Minor clinical signs evaluation and FOEM2 scoring module. The interface integrates clinical parameters with anatomical mapping of affected facial and intraoral regions to assist in objective severity assessment and localization of ischemic involvement. C. Evidence-based management guidance screen for confirmed or suspected vascular occlusion. The application provides recommended hyaluronidase dosing protocols, treatment mapping, adjunctive techniques, ultrasound-guided injection guidance, and loading dose recommendations to support standardized emergency management.

Figure 5. Vascular occlusion protocol interface. A. Protocols overview screen of the medical application displaying three structured emergency management categories: vascular occlusion, anaphylaxis, and late-onset adverse events. Each module provides access to detailed, stepwise treatment guidance for standardized complication management. B. Vascular occlusion protocol interface showing the internal subdivision into therapeutic sections. The screen provides structured access to evidence-based management components, including hyaluronidase administration, antiplatelet therapy, and corticosteroid treatment, allowing systematic consultation during emergency care.

Figure 6. Pharmacy module interface. A. Pharmacy section displaying preselected medications according to the emergency kit and ORA classification. The interface allows users to add and customize additional drugs as required. B. Individual medication profile within the pharmacy module showing barcode registration, pharmacologic characteristics, ORA classification, and customizable alerts for minimum stock and expiration dates, as well as records of drug entry, dispensing, and associated patient administration.

Figure 7. Home screen notification system displaying automated alerts generated by the application, including low hyaluronidase stock, impending medication expiration, and scheduled specialist appointments, supporting proactive clinical management and patient safety.

Figure 8: Specialist Directory and Appointment Scheduling Module. A. Specialists directory screen presenting searchable professional profiles with specialty information and integrated appointment booking functionality. B. Specialist appointment interface displaying available consultation dates and times, allowing users to select and schedule appointments with a chosen specialist.